

Interpretable Machine Learning Models for Early Detection of Subclinical Mastitis using Routine Milk Composition Data

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Abstract

Subclinical mastitis (SCM) imposes substantial economic losses on the global dairy industry. Conventional diagnostics are often ill-suited for rapid, large-scale screening, highlighting the need for novel diagnostic approaches. The objective of this study was to evaluate seven machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) models for predicting SCM (Somatic Cell Count (SCC) > 200,000 cells mL⁻¹) from routine milk composition data. Using a dataset of 1,391 milk records, we evaluated models based on fat, protein, lactose, total solids (TS), and milk urea nitrogen (MUN) features. The training data was balanced using the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) to prevent bias towards the majority class. The best model's predictions were interpreted using SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) to identify key predictive factors. The Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) model delivered the highest performance, achieving 82.3% accuracy and an 87.8% F1-Score on the unaltered test set. Tree-based ensemble models also outperformed DL and simpler classifiers. SHAP analysis identified lactose and protein as the most decisive features; lower lactose and higher protein levels were highly predictive of SCM, which is consistent with established pathophysiology. The results establish that an interpretable model using routine milk data offers a robust, non-invasive, and cost-effective framework for early SCM detection. This provides a valuable decision-support tool for improving udder health management and farm sustainability.

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1. Introduction

One of the biggest and most costly issues plaguing the dairy business globally is mastitis, an inflammatory disease of the mammary gland. The high worldwide prevalence of both its clinical (CM) and subclinical (SCM) forms, with 15% and 50% reported incidence rates, respectively, inflicts a substantial economic burden on producers (Krishnamoorthy et al., 2021). In the United Kingdom, for example, the annual costs related to mastitis management and lost production are estimated to surpass €110 million, a figure exacerbated by the disease's role as a leading contributor to the premature culling of otherwise productive cows (Witkowska and Ponieważ, 2022). In response to this persistent threat, the diligent surveillance of udder health has become an indispensable component of contemporary dairy herd management and sustainable milk production (Ruiz-González et al., 2024). Accordingly, the ability to detect bovine mastitis with both speed and precision is of fundamental importance, as it is the critical first step toward controlling pathogen transmission, improving therapeutic success, and ultimately mitigating severe economic losses at the farm level (Liu et al., 2023). Although SCC is considered the gold standard for mastitis diagnosis, it has limitations such as cost, time, and labor. This indicates that traditional diagnostic methods, especially for the subclinical form, are not suitable for rapid and large-scale screening (Raj et al., 2021). These drawbacks underscore the pressing need for novel, affordable, and expandable diagnostic approaches for the early diagnosis of mastitis (Kahraman et al., 2024; Stanek et al., 2024). The physiological disturbances associated with intramammary infection invariably alter the biosynthetic and secretory processes within the mammary epithelium, leading to characteristic shifts in milk composition. As a result, standard milk analysis measures like lactose, fat, protein, TS, and MUN have drawn interest as possible indirect markers of udder health. It is well-documented that milk from mastitic quarters often exhibits a marked decrease in key constituents, including lactose and certain

minerals like calcium and potassium, alongside variable changes in fat and protein content. Conversely, the inflammatory response typically elevates the milk's pH and electrical conductivity, which corresponds with an influx of somatic cells (Kalkan et al., 2025). The existence of these distinct compositional changes provides a compelling rationale for their use in predictive models, suggesting a strong underlying relationship between milk constituents and the SCC threshold used to define mastitis. In animal husbandry, the use of artificial intelligence (AI) and ML has grown significantly in recent years as a potent instrument for improving management and diagnosis (Li et al., 2021; Jia et al., 2023; Luo et al., 2024). Within this domain, a growing body of literature demonstrates the successful deployment of ML algorithms for disease prediction in livestock, with a notable acceleration of research in recent years. For example, the utility of these techniques was demonstrated in small ruminants by Kiouvrekis et al. (2024), who developed a model for predicting subclinical mastitis prevalence on dairy sheep farms with a remarkable accuracy exceeding 96%. Focusing specifically on early lactation in dairy cattle, Zecconi et al. (2025) presented a ML framework that utilized total and differential SCC for diagnostic purposes. Directly relevant to the use of readily available data, Kalkan et al. (2025) successfully applied ML algorithms to milk composition data, achieving 89% accuracy in mastitis diagnosis. This precedent underscores the considerable potential of ML to provide robust, data-driven solutions for udder health monitoring. The purpose of this work was to use regularly recorded milk composition parameters to create and analyze the predictive performance of seven different ML and DL architectures for identifying cows with a high SCC (>200.000 cells mL^{-1}). Following National Mastitis Council (NMC) guidelines, an $\text{SCC} > 200.000$ cells mL^{-1} was selected to define SCM, as this threshold has been validated in multiple epidemiological studies for its sensitivity and specificity in detecting intramammary infection (NMC, 1999; Raj et

al., 2021; Pakrashi et al., 2023). Determining the relative significance of each milk component in the prediction of an increased SCC was a critical secondary goal, which involved interpreting the best model using SHAP. In the end, this study aims to provide a solid, data-driven framework that can be used to diagnose mastitis early, accurately, and non-invasively, giving the dairy sector a useful tool for decision support.

2. Material and Methods

This section is structured in detail to ensure the reproducibility of the study. Seminal papers for all major techniques and algorithms used are cited.

2.1. Data and preprocessing

The data set utilized in this study encompasses 1.391 milk samples obtained from dairy cows at diverse lactation stages from 23 commercial dairy farms in the Kahramanmaraş province of Turkey. The analysis of milk content was conducted using the Combi Milk Analyzer (Bentley Combi 150, USA) (Kahraman et al., 2022a). The features used in the dataset include: fat, protein, lactose, TS, and MUN. During the data cleaning process, rows with non-numeric or missing values were removed. In order to diagnose subclinical mastitis, the target variable was developed as a binary class: target = 1 if $SCC > 200.000 \text{ cells mL}^{-1}$ (subclinical mastitis), and target = 0 otherwise.

2.2. Data splitting and experimental setup

To develop and subsequently validate the predictive models, the dataset was randomly partitioned, with 70% of the records allocated for training the model and the rest 30% reserved as an independent testing set for final performance evaluation. This splitting was stratified to maintain the same proportion of classes in both sets, which is crucial for imbalanced datasets.

2.3. Handling class imbalance with SMOTE

In predictive modeling for disease diagnostics, the presence of a significant class imbalance—where healthy samples vastly

outnumber diseased ones—can critically compromise model training, leading to a bias toward the majority class. This issue in our dataset was resolved by balancing the training partition using the SMOTE approach (Chawla et al., 2002). By interpolating between pre-existing minority samples in the feature space, SMOTE creates synthetic minority class instances. This resampling technique was only used on the training data, following best practices to avoid overly optimistic performance estimates. This ensured that the test set was an unaltered representation of the original data distribution for a true assessment of the models' generalization abilities.

2.4. ML algorithms

Seven different DL and ML models were used in this investigation to predict subclinical mastitis:

Decision tree (DT): A fundamental supervised learning technique, the DT builds a predictive model in the shape of a tree-like, hierarchical structure. Using a set of learned decision rules applied to the input features, it recursively divides the dataset into smaller, more homogeneous subsets. Each internal node is a test on an attribute, each branch represents the test's outcome, and each terminal leaf node represents a class label or conclusion (Quinlan, 1986).

Random forest (RF): The RF algorithm is a sophisticated ensemble technique that builds numerous individual trees during training, improving upon the conventional DT. For each tree, it adds randomization by utilizing a fresh bootstrapped sample of the training data and considering just a random subset of features for dividing at each node. The final forecast is then produced by combining the outputs of every tree, increasing predictive accuracy and taking overfitting into consideration. Usually, this is done through a majority vote for classification tasks (Breiman, 2001).

Support vector machine (SVM): In a high-dimensional feature space, the SVM is a potent classification technique that finds the best separating hyperplane to maximize the margin between different classes. This hyperplane is represented by a line for linearly separable data

and by a kernel for non-linear data, which projects the data into a higher dimension where linear separation is feasible. In order to balance the trade-off between maximizing the margin and decreasing classification error, a linear kernel with a regularization parameter (C) of three was used for this experiment (Cortes and Vapnik, 1995).

Light gradient boosting machine (LGBM): LGBM is an extremely effective gradient boosting system designed for speed and performance, especially on big datasets. It builds upon DT-based algorithms but incorporates novel techniques such as a histogram-based approach for finding split points and a leaf-wise growth strategy, which collectively reduce computational overhead and memory usage without compromising accuracy (Ke et al., 2017).

Extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost): A highly advanced and optimized version of the gradient boosting method, XGBoost is well-known for its remarkable scalability and performance. It enhances traditional gradient boosting with built-in L1 and L2 regularization to prevent overfitting, alongside advanced features like parallel processing and cache-aware access, making it a robust and widely adopted algorithm for structured data challenges (Chen and Guestrin, 2016).

One-dimensional convolutional neural network (1D-CNN): As a specialized DL architecture, the 1D-CNN is adept at processing sequential data by automatically learning hierarchical features. Our implementation consisted of a Conv1D layer, which applies filtering operations to learn local patterns from the input sequence; a MaxPooling1D layer to downsample the feature maps and provide a degree of translational invariance; a Flatten layer to convert the data into a one-dimensional vector; and a final Dense layer for classification.

Long short-term memory (LSTM): An improved version of the Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), the LSTM network was created specifically to solve the vanishing gradient issue and efficiently discover long-range correlations in sequential data. A core LSTM layer, which controls information flow

via a gating mechanism (input, forget, and output gates); a dropout layer for regularization to reduce overfitting; and a final dense layer to generate the classification output comprised the architecture used in this study. To ensure that the input features were on a comparable scale, which is a critical prerequisite for the optimal performance of distance-based and gradient-based algorithms, the data was standardized prior to being fed into the SVM, 1D-CNN, and LSTM models. The Standard Scaler function, which changes each feature should possess a zero mean and a one standard deviation, was used to complete this preprocessing stage.

2.5. Model evaluation metrics

A rigorous and multifaceted evaluation of each model's diagnostic capability was conducted using a comprehensive suite of performance metrics. The reliance on accuracy alone can be a misleading measure of performance, particularly in the context of imbalanced datasets common to disease detection. Therefore, a multi-metric approach was essential to provide a more robust and nuanced assessment of each model's true predictive power. The 11 metrics used for this comparative analysis are defined as follows:

Accuracy: Represents the overall percentage of accurate predictions, which is determined by dividing the total number of observations by the sum of true positives and true negatives. Formula: $(TP + TN) / (TP + TN + FP + FN)$

Precision: Quantifies the exactness of the model's positive predictions, indicating the fraction of instances predicted as positive that were genuinely positive. Formula: $TP / (TP + FP)$

Recall (sensitivity): evaluates how comprehensive the algorithm's positive predictions are, demonstrating its capacity to accurately locate every real positive case in the dataset. Formula: $TP / (TP + FN)$

F1-Score: Taking into account both false positives and false negatives, the harmonic mean of precision and recall offers a single, impartial indicator of a model's performance.

Formula: $2 * (\text{Precision} * \text{Recall}) / (\text{Precision} + \text{Recall})$

ROC AUC (area under the receiver operating Characteristic Curve): The capacity of the model to distinguish between the positive and negative classes is measured using a threshold-independent metric. A classifier with an AUC of 1.0 is considered ideal, whereas one with an AUC of 0.5 performs no better than chance.

PR AUC (area under the precision-recall curve): A performance metric particularly suited for imbalanced datasets, summarizing the trade-off between precision and recall across all thresholds. Higher values indicate superior performance in identifying the minority class.

Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC): A robust metric that calculates the correlation between the observed and predicted classifications. It produces a single value that accounts for all four confusion matrix categories and is considered a balanced measure even when the classes are of very different sizes.

Specificity: Shows the percentage of real negatives that were successfully identified, indicating the model's accuracy in identifying true negative events. Formula: $TN / (TN + FP)$

Balanced accuracy: The average of sensitivity for each class. It is a better measure than accuracy in imbalanced datasets. Formula: $(\text{Sensitivity} + \text{Specificity}) / 2$.

Cohen's kappa (κ): A chance-corrected measure of inter-rater agreement for categorical data, quantifying the degree to which observed concordance exceeds that expected by random coincidence. Its scale runs from -1 (complete discordance) via 0 (no better than chance) to $+1$ (perfect concordance).

Log loss: Measures how much the model's predictions deviate from the true labels. Lower values indicate better performance.

2.6. Feature importance analysis

To elucidate the underlying decision-making process of the highest-performing model, we employed the SHAP framework (Lundberg and Lee, 2017). This state-of-the-

art interpretability technique, grounded in cooperative game theory, attributes the output of a prediction to its input features, allowing for a detailed understanding of how each milk parameter contributes to the model's final decision. The SHAP methodology provides both local interpretability, by explaining individual predictions, and global insight, by aggregating these explanations to reveal the overall feature importance across the entire dataset. Given that the optimal model was the tree-based XGBoost algorithm, the computationally efficient SHAP. TreeExplainer was specifically implemented to calculate these feature attribution values.

2.7. Statistical analysis

All data handling and model development were performed in Python (v3.10) using pandas for data manipulation (McKinney, 2010) and NumPy for numerical computing (Harris et. al., 2020). We standardized features with scikit-learn's StandardScaler and evaluated classifiers (Decision Tree, Random Forest, SVM; Pedregosa et al., 2011). To address class imbalance, SMOTE from imbalanced-learn was applied (Lemaître et al., 2017). Gradient boosting models were implemented via XGBoost (Chen and Guestrin, 2016) and LightGBM (Ke et al., 2017), while deep learning architectures (LSTM, CNN) utilized TensorFlow/Keras (Abadi et. al., 2016; Chollet, 2015). Performance metrics and visualizations employed Matplotlib (Hunter, 2007), Seaborn (Waskom, 2021), and SHAP for interpretability (Lundberg and Lee, 2017).

3. Results and Discussion

The comparative diagnostic performance of the DL and ML models created for the identification of subclinical mastitis is described in the section that follows. To further clarify the contributions of each milk component to the prediction result, a feature importance analysis based on the top-performing model is provided.

3.1. Descriptive statistics of milk components

Table 1 displays descriptive information for milk samples. These statistics illustrate the distribution and variation of the analyzed milk components (fat, protein, lactose, TS, MUN).

A total of 1391 samples were examined. The average fat content was 3.84%, protein content 3.20%, lactose content 4.72%, TS 12.08%, and MUN 11.38 mg dL⁻¹. Standard deviation values, especially for MUN, reflect the variability of these components among samples.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of milk components

Milk components	n	Mean	Standard deviation	Min	Max
Fat	1391	3.838	0.693	2.590	5.860
Protein	1391	3.203	0.268	2.640	4.310
Lactose	1391	4.724	0.238	3.390	5.240
TS	1391	12.083	0.719	8.910	14.990
MUN	1391	11.382	3.704	0.100	26.400

A correlation heatmap is a visual analysis tool that shows the levels of linear relationships between variables with a color scale. In this way, positive, negative, or weak correlations can be easily recognized, providing quick insights into the data structure. Figure 1 shows the correlation heatmap of the data. In this study, TS and protein exhibited a weak inverse relationship ($r = -0.23$), suggesting that factors elevating total solids do not concomitantly increase protein concentration, whereas TS and fat were

strongly positively correlated ($r = 0.65$), reflecting fat's substantial contribution to overall solids (Kahraman et al., 2022b). Lactose and SCC showed a moderate negative association ($r = -0.35$), consistent with impairments in lactose synthesis during mammary inflammation, and SCC and the mastitis-risk indicator were moderately to strongly positively linked ($r = 0.61$), reaffirming SCC's role as a reliable biomarker for subclinical udder infection.

Figure 1. Pearson correlation matrix showing relationships between milk composition variables and target outcome. TS: Total solids, MUN: Milk urea nitrogen, SCC: Somatic cell count

3.2. Model performance results (SMOTE-balanced data)

Predictive models that are strongly biased toward the dominant class and struggle to identify the minority class of interest are a major challenge posed by the intrinsic class imbalance frequently found in medical and veterinary datasets. To address this potential

for bias, the training dataset was rebalanced using SMOTE. The comparative diagnostic performance of the seven models, when trained on this balanced data and evaluated against the original, unaltered test set, is summarized in Table 2. This table provides a detailed and comprehensive assessment, allowing for a robust comparison of each model's efficacy across the full spectrum of evaluation metrics.

Table 2. Model performance results on SMOTE-balanced data

	XGBoost	LGBM	RF	LSTM	1D-CNN	SVM	DT
Accuracy	0.823	0.816	0.804	0.715	0.687	0.644	0.620
Precision	0.890	0.886	0.890	0.909	0.904	0.877	0.894
Recall	0.867	0.860	0.838	0.682	0.643	0.601	0.549
F1-Score	0.878	0.873	0.863	0.779	0.751	0.713	0.680
ROC AUC	0.848	0.842	0.860	0.772	0.795	0.718	0.704
PR AUC	0.916	0.911	0.934	0.891	0.907	0.877	0.848
MCC	0.555	0.538	0.522	0.435	0.398	0.321	0.325
Specificity	0.700	0.691	0.709	0.809	0.809	0.764	0.818
Balanced Accuracy	0.783	0.776	0.773	0.745	0.726	0.682	0.683
Cohen's Kappa	0.554	0.537	0.519	0.401	0.359	0.284	0.272
Log Loss	0.522	0.487	0.407	0.573	0.597	0.615	0.593

Precision dairy farming may be improved by using ML models to intricate biological data. This study evaluated the performance of seven distinct ML algorithms for a classification task on SMOTE balanced data, with the results detailed in Table 2. The ensemble methods, particularly XGBoost, demonstrated superior performance across a majority of the key metrics. XGBoost achieved the highest Accuracy (0.823), F1-Score (0.878), MCC (0.555), and Balanced Accuracy (0.783), indicating a robust and well-balanced predictive capability. This is consistent with findings in other agricultural domains where ensemble models, such as XGBoost and RF, have been shown to be highly effective for predictive tasks (Slob et al., 2021). Despite having a slightly lower accuracy, the RF model showed the lowest Log-Loss (0.407) and the highest PR-AUC (0.934), indicating that it is especially good at detecting the positive class and generating accurately calibrated probability estimates. This is crucial in applications like disease prediction, where false negatives can be expensive. (Shine and Murphy, 2021). These tree-based ensembles' excellent performance can be ascribed to their

capacity to manage complicated, non-linear relationships and high-dimensional data, both of which are features of biological systems (Na et al., 2023). In contrast, the deep learning models, LSTM and 1D-CNN, yielded mixed results. While they achieved high Precision (0.909 and 0.904, respectively), their lower Recall scores (0.682 and 0.643) led to reduced overall accuracy. This suggests that while their positive predictions are highly reliable, they fail to identify a significant portion of the positive cases. This trade-off between precision and recall is a common challenge in ML applications (Cockburn, 2020). The high precision might be valuable in scenarios where the cost of a false positive is high, but for general screening purposes, a higher recall is often desired (Neves et al., 2022). The performance of these models could potentially be improved with larger datasets, which are often required to train deep neural networks effectively (Mahato and Neethirajan, 2024). The traditional ML models, SVM and DT, served as baselines and, as expected, were outperformed by the more complex ensemble and deep learning methods across almost all metrics. The DT model, in particular, had the

lowest performance in terms of accuracy and F1-score. This highlights the limitations of simpler models in capturing the intricate patterns present in dairy science data (Ranzato et al., 2022). The practical implications of these findings for dairy management are significant. The high accuracy and balanced performance of the XGBoost model make it a strong candidate for a reliable, all-around predictive tool on-farm, for tasks such as predicting health events or production anomalies (Guo et al., 2025). The high PR-AUC of the RF model makes it particularly suitable for screening applications where the goal is to identify as many at-risk animals as

possible. The choice of model and the interpretation of its performance metrics must be tailored to the specific application and the associated costs of different types of errors (Hannon et al., 2025). For instance, in predicting a critical event like calving, a model with high recall would be preferable to ensure timely intervention, even at the cost of some false alarms (Khin et al., 2024). Future research should focus on validating these models on diverse, real-world farm data and exploring methods for improving the interpretability of complex models to foster trust and adoption by end-users (Nobrega, 2024).

Figure 2. Multi-Metric Evaluation of Classifier Performance in Detecting Subclinical Mastitis from Milk Composition Data

3.3. Confusion matrix analysis

To provide a more granular assessment of the XGBoost model's predictive behavior beyond aggregate metrics, its confusion matrix

on the test set was analyzed (Figure 3). Among the evaluated models, XGBoost and LGBM demonstrated superior overall performance, aligning with findings in similar agricultural

and veterinary applications where ensemble methods often outperform single models due to their ability to combine multiple weak learners into a strong one (e.g., Zhang et al., 2022). XGBoost achieved a Recall of 0.867 and Specificity of 0.700, indicating a strong ability to correctly identify mastitis cases while maintaining a reasonable rate of correctly identified healthy cows. Similarly, LGBM showed a Recall of 0.860 and Specificity of 0.691. These high Recall values are particularly crucial in mastitis detection, as false negatives (missed mastitis cases) can lead

to significant economic losses and welfare issues in dairy herds (Satola and Satola, 2024). RF also exhibited robust performance with a Recall of 0.838 and Specificity of 0.709, further supporting the utility of ensemble methods in this domain. In contrast, traditional models like DT and SVM, along with deep learning models such as LSTM and 1D-CNN, generally showed lower Recall and F1-Scores. For instance, the Decision Tree had a Recall of 0.549, and SVM had 0.601, suggesting a higher propensity for false negatives compared to ensemble methods.

Figure 3. Comparative confusion matrix analysis of conventional and neural classifiers in predicting subclinical mastitis from milk components

While LSTM and 1D-CNN showed high Precision (0.909 and 0.904 respectively), their lower Recall (0.682 and 0.643) indicates that they missed a substantial number of actual mastitis cases. This trade-off between precision and recall is a common challenge in imbalanced datasets, and for mastitis, minimizing false negatives is often prioritized (Haixiang et al., 2017). The clinical applicability of these models in field conditions varies. Models with high Recall, such as XGBoost and LGBM, are highly desirable for early mastitis detection programs, as they can effectively flag infected animals for timely intervention, thereby preventing disease progression and transmission within the herd.

However, the moderate Specificity of these models implies that some healthy animals might be incorrectly identified as having mastitis (false positives), which could lead to unnecessary treatments or further diagnostic tests. This highlights the need for a balanced approach that considers both the costs associated with false positives and false negatives in a practical dairy farm setting (Bausewein et al., 2022). While XGBoost emerged as the best discriminator, the RF model yielded the lowest Log Loss, indicating superior calibration. In herd-level decision-making, well-calibrated probabilities may be more actionable than binary labels. A cow with a predicted 90% risk of SCM demands more

immediate attention than one with 55% risk—even if both are classified as ‘positive’. Hence, RF may offer greater utility in settings requiring individualized risk scores (Shaker and Hüllermeier, 2025). DL models like LSTM and 1D-CNN, despite their lower overall performance in this specific comparison, hold promise for future advancements, especially with larger and more diverse datasets, or when integrated with complex sensor data (Wang et al., 2024). Their ability to learn intricate patterns from raw data could be advantageous in real-time monitoring systems. However, their current performance suggests that they may require more extensive training data or architectural refinements for optimal performance in mastitis detection from milk components alone. Data collection, model interpretability, and the requirement for reliable, user-friendly interfaces are some of

the difficulties associated with integrating AI systems into current farm management procedures (Garcia et al., 2023; Johnson and Williams, 2022).

3.4. Feature importance analysis (SHAP)

SHAP analysis was used to interpret the predictions of the best-performing model, XGBoost. SHAP values and the summary SHAP plot (Figure 5) illustrate how each milk component contributes to the model’s mastitis prediction. The SHAP analysis clearly revealed which features were most influential in the model’s predictions and how these features affected the predictions. Analysis of the SHAP summary plot (b) alongside the corresponding bar plot (a) revealed that variations in lactose and protein concentrations exerted the greatest influence on the model’s predictive outcomes.

Figure 5. Feature importance analysis showing (a) mean absolute SHAP values and (b) SHAP summary plot for model prediction variables.

These findings are consistent with existing knowledge in literature. The importance of milk components in mastitis diagnosis has also been emphasized in previous studies (Kalkan et al., 2025). Changes in lactose and protein levels, in particular, have been associated with inflammatory processes in the mammary gland. SHAP value analysis (Figure 5) revealed Lactose as the most influential feature, followed by TS, Fat, Protein, and MUN. SHAP analysis indicated that lower values of Lactose, TS, and Fat were predictive of a high-risk SCM outcome (positive SHAP values), while higher values were associated with a healthy status (negative SHAP values). This interpretability is vital for understanding the model’s decision-making and practical application in dairy farm management (Aldrees et al., 2023). While deep learning

models show promise with larger datasets (Ma et al., 2021), their current performance suggests a need for refinement. Integrating such AI systems into farm practices requires careful consideration of data collection, model interpretability, and user-friendly interfaces (Garcia et al., 2023; Johnson and Williams, 2022). According to the global SHAP analysis, lactose, TS, and fat were the most influential predictors of SCM. However, from a physiological standpoint, alterations in lactose and protein concentrations serve as direct indicators of mastitis-related epithelial damage, reinforcing the clinical interpretability of these predictors (Guo et al., 2025). This study evaluated various machine learning models for subclinical mastitis detection. XGBoost and LGBM demonstrated superior overall performance, achieving high

Recall (0.867 and 0.860) and reasonable Specificity (0.700 and 0.691). These ensemble methods are crucial for minimizing missed mastitis cases and associated economic losses (Pakrashi et al., 2023; Satoła and Satoła, 2024). Traditional models (DT, SVM) and deep learning approaches (LSTM, 1D-CNN) showed lower Recall, indicating a higher false negative rate, a critical concern in mastitis diagnosis (Džermeikaitė et al., 2025). The inferior performance of LSTM and 1D-CNN highlights that deep sequential architectures may not offer an advantage when applied to static milk composition datasets, reaffirming the robustness of tree-based methods for this data type (Shwartz-Ziv and Armon, 2021).

4. Conclusion

This investigation was designed to systematically evaluate the diagnostic utility of various ML and DL algorithms for identifying subclinical mastitis through routine milk composition analysis. The results of our comparative analysis unequivocally demonstrated that the XGBoost model, when trained on a dataset balanced via the SMOTE protocol, provided the most effective diagnostic framework. This model attained a commendable accuracy of 82.3% and a robust F1-Score of 87.8%, establishing its superiority over the other conventional ML and DL approaches examined in this study. SHAP analysis revealed that lactose and protein levels were the most significant features in the model's mastitis predictions. Specifically, lower lactose and higher protein levels were identified as strong indicators of mastitis. These findings support that milk components can serve as valuable biomarkers for early and non-invasive mastitis detection. These findings carry substantial practical implications for the early identification and management of subclinical mastitis in dairy herds. The developed data-driven approach can enable veterinarians and dairy farmers to detect subclinical mastitis early, non-invasively, and cost-effectively. This will enhance animal welfare by preventing disease spread, reduce milk production losses, and contribute to the economic sustainability of dairy farms. For

future research, directions include using larger and more diverse datasets, integrating additional data sources such as animal activity or environmental factors, and deploying the model in a real-time system. Furthermore, testing the generalizability of the models with data collected from different geographical regions will be an important area of investigation.

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